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Executive Summary

This document provides a list of Coronal Mass Ejections (CMEs) that produced intense particle radiation and were selected by the **SPEARHEAD** consortium as interesting events to study in depth during the project. The selected events fulfilled a number of criteria that are detailed in the present report. The project aims to bring together many different datasets in order to study a wide range of physical processes influencing intense radiations. During Task 4.1 we reviewed the available data and identified CMEs that could be studied from different angles in order to reach a more comprehensive understanding of what controls the production of high-energy radiation. This list marks the first step in the **SPEARHEAD** event analysis tasks, it is not set in stone and will no doubt evolve during the project as solar maximum progresses and provides additional events observed by Parker Solar Probe, Solar Orbiter and soon the PUNCH mission.

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1 Introduction

The **SPEARHEAD** project must perform a comprehensive study of high energy particle observations in the heliosphere (>100 MeV/nucleon ions and >1 MeV electrons) with the aim to answer three main science questions:

- **SQ1: How are ions and electrons accelerated to the highest energies in solar eruptions, beyond 100 MeV/n and 1 MeV, respectively?**
- **SQ2: What are the processes governing particle release** from acceleration sites in the solar corona?
- **SQ3: What are the key processes of high-energy particle transport** in the interplanetary medium, in the magnetosphere and in the atmosphere?

In order to address these questions on particle acceleration and transport, the different work packages must analyze intense solar events from different angles combining a broad range of modeling and data mining techniques through the systematic exploitation of remote-sensing data (imaging, electromagnetic radiation detectors) and in situ data at different locations in the heliosphere. WP4 aims at providing the general context for each event of interest and as such imposes a set of constraints on the different events that can actually be analyzed including the necessary availability of key datasets. Beyond the experimental context and their observational limitations, event to event variability was also a key factor in the decision process and discussed with the whole consortium.

In order to address the scientific questions of the project listed above, the available data for each event must be sufficient:

- **to derive the properties of key CME structures involved in particle acceleration (SQ1)** such as coronal shock waves that are serious contenders to the production of high-energy particles. Remote-sensing data in extreme ultraviolet and white-light imagery must be available to derive the 3-D structure of shock waves as well as their drivers in regions of the corona that cannot be explored with in situ detectors. In situ data must be available to measure some intense shocks and flux ropes directly in situ providing 'ground truth' on the local properties of CMEs.
- **to derive particle release conditions (SQ2)** close to the Sun and in the interplanetary medium. In order to study particle release from the solar corona (Q2), we must exploit jointly surface magnetograms as boundary conditions to numerical modelling of the solar atmosphere as well as remote-sensing data that could provide clues on the reconfiguration of the solar corona in operation during the release of particles. The release time of accelerated particles can be provided by radio spectrograms, high-energy electromagnetic radiation (gamma, hard X-ray) and in situ data.
- **to derive particle transport conditions (SQ3)** we must be able to model and measure the state of the solar wind through which these particles propagate. This involves again the exploitation of magnetograms as boundary conditions in combination with direct in situ data in the solar wind. The project aims at better understanding the modulation of extra-solar high-energy radiation such as galactic cosmic rays in response to Earth impacting CMEs. This requires detailed measurements of CMEs near Earth as well as high-quality measurements of GCRs.

A common requirement in order to address all scientific questions listed above is the necessary availability of in situ measurements of high-energy particles. This was central to the decision process and a number of readily available particle data were considered from a broad range of spacecraft. In addition, complementary datasets that are able to fill the gap in the energy spectral region from beyond the nominal science-grade spacecraft instrument capabilities up to that of ground-based recordings were also considered. The ERNE instrument for instance can provide measurements in that range. Even though the data is not yet calibrated, the count rates were considered providing additional criteria to select one event over another.

This event list is a stepping-stone towards addressing some key objectives of the project

- the scientific analysis results on (i) the catalogued SEP/GLE and FD events using direct observational and statistical methods, and on (ii) a selected subset of the best-observed events using analytical methods;
- data analysis and visualisation tools enabling the coordinated analysis of high energy particle data and contexts observations;
- a significant number of open-access scientific publications on the scientific results as well as tools and data products;

CME Selection Process and the CME list

In this section, the selection process is detailed further and the CME list is provided with for each event some salient aspects of each CME that we plan to address during the project.

A catalogue of high-energy SEP events, based on a systematic search of proton data at >100 MeV observed by **SOHO** ERNE in the years 1997-2024 is being compiled within SPEARHEAD and corresponds to the first deliverable of WP5. A total of **169 proton events** with significant particle fluxes above 100 MeV have already been identified in this catalogue. Because a very detailed analysis involving reconstructions and modelling of the solar origin of each event WP4 would be impractical, the approach has been to divide the WP4 in two main activities:

- For each event in the >100 MeV catalogue we will analyse remote-sensing observations for electromagnetic signatures of the associated flare (gamma rays, hard X-rays and soft X-rays and radio), CME (white-light), past shock reconstructions (described in the next section). In doing so we will use a very broad range of data taken from ground-based and spaceborne facilities.
- Select a subset of events that will be analysed in more depth ('priority events'). The selection process is detailed below (section 1.2).

1.1 Deriving key properties of CMEs for particle acceleration

1.1.1 Coronal Shock Modeling

The reconstructions of 3-D shock are based on multi-point imaging [Rouillard et al. 2016, Kouloumvakos et al. 2019] and provide the 3-D shock expansion speed. Multi-point imaging can be a combination of datasets from SDO-AIA, SoHO-LASCO, STEREO-SECCHI, Solar Orbiter EUVI, METIS, SoHO-HI and PSP-WISPR **which were all considered in establishing the current list**. In addition to exploiting the velocity derived by the 3-D fitting technique, the properties of the background corona and solar wind must also be provided by global MHD models in order to determine shock parameters (Mach numbers, compression ratios, shock normal angle). For that we have two Alfvén-wave driven 3-D MHD models of the corona available, the UPS-led Wind-Predict 3-D MHD model [Réville et al. 2021] and the Predictive Sciences Inc-led MAST model [Lionello et al. 2009]. Depending on availability we will choose between these two models and if both are available we will then be able to compare their results. The models will be used to determine when and where on the 3-D shock a particle detector measuring the strong SEPs (considered in WP3 and WP5) will be connected magnetically, by tracing magnetic field lines from the spacecraft back to the shock surface in the 3-D MHD model. In order to run these models we must have high-quality magnetograms available, **this was integrated in the decision process for each event**.

To fulfil the combined requirements imposed by shock triangulation and 3-D MHD modelling we restricted the current list to solar events that occurred after the launches of the STEREO spacecraft and SDO, that is after 2010.

1.1.2 Coronal Flux Rope Modeling

In addition to modelling their coronal shock waves, we may need to fit the flux ropes of a subset of CME events for specific studies. This requires similar multi-point imaging to the previous shock-fitting task but an additional requirement is that the flux rope be easily discernible in the coronal imaging. This is not always true and we decided to flag events for which the fitting is clear enough that a good flux rope orientation can be derived.

1.1.3 Interplanetary Shock and Flux Rope Modeling

A subset of CME shocks and flux ropes may need to be modelled in the interplanetary medium, this will be carried in different ways. The most complete way available in toolkit of the SPEARHEAD project will consist in fitting the flux rope and shock wave in the solar corona until about 10-15 solar radii and then injecting this flux rope and the shock into 3-D MHD interplanetary simulations using the HELIOCAST model (Réville et al. 2023): heliocast.irap.omp.eu

These fits will provide quantitative estimates of key CME properties and its substructures such as the coronal shock wave.

1.2 Event list

The following list of priority events is the result of careful consideration of the list of > 100 MeV SEP events being developed in WP5. As the project progresses, this list of SEPs will grow due to the continued high level of solar activity, and our list of priority events may also grow.

A turning point in our analysis of the solar context of SEP events occurred during the solar minimum period of 2006-2009 and the rising phase of the previous solar cycle with:

- the launch of the twin **STEREO** spacecraft in 2006, which allowed the analysis of CME from multiple angles, and thus the precise determination of CME sources and directions, as well as their sub-components (shocks, flux lines).
- the launch of the **Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO)** in early 2010, which provided for the first time high-cadence, full-disk imaging of flare CME formations and shock expansions,
- the launch of the **Fermi** spacecraft in 2008, which enabled a more systematic sensing of solar gamma rays.

Recent years have also been marked by the arrival of unprecedented data from the first mission to enter the solar corona, Parker Solar Probe, and the Solar Orbiter mission.

Prior to 2007, the solar context of >100MeV SEPs was not well constrained, and *the project decided to focus its attention on the subset of events that occurred after 2007*. This included some **80 SEP events** which remained too large a pool of event to undertake detailed studies of their solar context.

Further criteria for the selection of the events were then applied in order to downsize our sample to a more manageable dozen events:

- an event *had to be observed in EUV and white-light* by **at least two spacecraft simultaneously** in order to allow localisation of the sources (flares, shocks),
- *all GLEs* that occurred since 2007 **had to be included** in the analysis by default and were associated with such strong CMEs that the previous criterion was automatically met,
- priority was then placed on **SEP events that occurred in isolation** to limit the uncertainties in determining SEP onset times, except for the complex sequence of the SEP events of May 2024 that is kept due to its historical geomagnetic storm,
- *certain events* had to occur *in conjunction with high-energy radiation* such as **gamma-ray and hard X-ray emissions**,
- additional criteria were also considered associated with the specific science goals of the project were considered such as having: (1) *solar origins on the far-side of the Sun with occulted flares to isolate better the shock contribution of the SEP*, (2) *the detection of strong SEPs inside magnetic flux ropes in order to address the topic of GLEs occurring during Forbusch*

decreases, (3) clear ICME impacts at the very inner heliosphere by Parker Solar Probe and Solar Orbiter.

These criteria guided our preliminary analysis of each event was carried out in order to isolate important high-energy processes that **SPEARHEAD** aims to better understand. The result of this selection process is given below where we classified our events according to whether they were GLE events and whether they occurred on the far side of the Sun. For example the recently detected GLE on 11/05/2024 and the sub-GLE on 08/06/2024 were selected as part of the event list.

This list was further refined during **SPEARHEAD Workshop #1** (11-13/06/2024) and the team then proceeded to prioritise the events in order to determine which ones would be analysed first during the project (P1 events) and those considered for a later stage (P2 events). Five events were considered as top priority for the coming 18 months.

Table 0-1: The list of high-energy radiation solar events selected by the SPEARHEAD team for further study during the project

EVENT DATE	PRIORITY	GLE?	FORBUSH DECREASE?	EUV/WHITE-LIGHT OBSERVATIONS	HXR/GAMMA ?	INTENS E SEP?	INTERESTING ASPECT ?	FAR SIDE
13-12-2006	P2 (2025-2026)	70	Yes (15/12 @Oulu NM)	NOT GOOD	?	YES	ISOLATED EVENT, NICE IN ERNE	NO
21-03-2011	P1 (2024-2025)	?	No	VERY GOOD	?	YES AT STEREO-A	ISOLATED, WIDESPREAD SEP	YES
07-03-2012	P2 (2025-2026)	SUB-GLE	YES LONG LASTING	VERY GOOD	GAMMA-RAY EVENT	yes at EPHIN	NICE SHOCK IN IMAGERY	NO
12-7-2012	P1 (2024-2025)	NO	SIMPLE SHORT	VERY GOOD	?	NO	ISOLATED, ERNE GOOD DATA	NO
23-7-2012	P2 (2025-2026)	NO	NO	VERY GOOD	NO FAR SIDE	CARRINGTON LIKE EVENT	HIGH RADIATION PRESSURE	YES
17-05-2012	P1 (2024-2025)	71	no	VERY GOOD	?	YES	GLE, ISOLATED EVENT, CONNECTIVITY FR, INTERESTING LOSS CONE DIST	NO

01-09-2014	P2 (2025-2026)	NO	NO	VERY GOOD	INTENSE GAMMA EVENT	YES	ISOLATED, WIDESPREAD SEP, ERNE VERY SMOOTH	YES (VERY)
20-06-2015	P2 (2025-2026)	NO	YES LONG LASTING	GOOD	?	NO (@ Earth)	COMPOUND STREAM	NO
10-09-2017	P2 (2025-2026)	72	NO	GOOD	GAMMA-RAY EVENT	YES	ISOLATED WEST LIMB	NOISE
17-7-2021	P2 (2025-2026)	NO	NO	VERY GOOD	GAMMA-RAY EVENT	? (NO @ Earth)	?	YES (VERY)
28-10-2021	P2 (2025-2026)	73	no	VERY GOOD	?	YES	?	?
2-11-2021	P1 (2024-2025)	?	YES	VERY GOOD	?	?	Nice FD, multispacecraft (SOLO & L1)	?
11-05-2024	P1 (2024-2025)	74	YES, strong	GOOD	?	YES	GLE coincided with the FD deep phase + strong magnetospheric effect for mid/low-lat NMs	

The orbital configuration of each event and the most interesting aspects/characteristics of each event are given in the following Figures.

BEHIND THE LIMB P1 EVENTS

21-03-2011

8

- ISOLATED EVENT
- VERY GOOD IMAGERY
- STRONG SEP STA & L1
- NO GAMMA/HXR
- NO GLE

23-07-2012

6

- ISOLATED EVENT
- CARRINGTON-TYPE
- VERY GOOD IMAGERY
- POWERFUL SEP STA, WEAK SEP L1
- NO GAMMA EVENT ?
- NO GLE

01-09-2014

7

- ISOLATED EVENT
- VERY GOOD IMAGERY
- STRONG SEP STA & STB
- GAMMA-RAY EVENT

17-07-2021

3

- VERY GOOD IMAGERY
- SEPs AT SoIO AND BEPI
- GAMMA-RAY EVENTS

Figure 0-1 – Selected behind the limb P1 events. Each figure that depicts the configuration of the spacecraft relevant to the Sun was constructed utilizing Solar-MACH tool (see Gieseler et al., 2022)

GLE P1 EVENTS

17-05-2012

5

- VERY GOOD IMAGERY
- STRONG SEP STA & L1
- GLE 71 INSIDE FR
- GAMMA-RAY EVENT
- FR MAGNETIC CONNECTION

28-10-2021

8

- CARRINGTON-TYPE
- VERY GOOD IMAGERY
- GLE 73
- EARTH-DIRECTED FD ON 2ND NOV?
- STRONG SEP ALL AROUND
- GAMMA-RAY EVENT

11-05-2024

1

- GLE74
- EARTH-DIRECTED (FD)
- GOOD IMAGERY
- STRONG SEP EARTH
- GLE INSIDE FR?
- GAMMA-RAY EVENT ?

Figure 0-2 – Similar to Figure 0-1 but for the selected P1 GLE events

OTHER P1 EVENTS

02-11-2021

9

- VERY GOOD IMAGERY
- WEAK SEP STA & L1
- NICE FD
- NO GAMMA

12-07-2012

4

- EXCELLENT IMAGERY (FR/SOCK)
- WEAK SEP
- NICE FD

08-06-2024 (ON GOING) 1

- GOOD IMAGERY (FR/SOCK)
- STRONG SEP
- DIRECTED PSP
- GAMMA EVENT?
- GLE?

Figure 0-3 – Similar to Figure 0-1 but for the selected P1 events that are not GLEs

P2 EVENTS

07-03-2012

13

- VERY GOOD IMAGERY
- SUB GLE
- STRONG SEP
- STRONG GAMMA EVENT
- STRONG FD

20-06-2015

12

- STRONG FD
- NO SEP
- COMPOUND STREAM AT L1

10-09-2017

11

- VERY GOOD IMAGERY
- GLE 72
- STRONG SEP
- GAMMA EVENT
- NO

Figure 0-4 – Similar to Figure 0-1 but for the selected P2 events

1.3 Description of the first events to be analysed in the project

Event 1: 10th -11th of May 2024 Mother's Day Superstorm

A strong shock and complex solar ejecta hit the Earth's magnetosphere on 10th May 2024 leading to the strongest geomagnetic storm since the 2003 Halloween superstorm. Upon the arrival of the Coronal Mass Ejections (CMEs) at Earth, ground-based neutron monitors around the globe recorded a strong Forbush decrease in response to the shielding effects of these CMEs on the galactic cosmic ray (GCR) fluxes. As the cosmic ray fluxes reached a minimum on May 11 at 01:00UT, a Ground Level Enhancement - GLE74 - was suddenly detected¹ together with a powerful Solar Energetic Particle (SEP) event measured at the Lagrange L1 point and at the Solar-Terrestrial Relations Observatory Ahead (STEREO-A). This GLE was triggered by an X5.8 flare and a fast CME (>1500 km/s) originating in the complex active region NOAA13668 (S15W55). Evidently this is a very disturbed period and thus very complex and challenging. However, there are observations available from multiple particle observers in-situ which can be combined with imagery data. To this end SPEARHEAD will:

- Carry out an observational analysis of this complex sequence of events including the state of the interplanetary medium during this powerful radiation storm and the properties of the measured GLE on the ground by neutron monitors and the strong SEP in the interplanetary space.
- Work on a timing analysis of the in-situ particle recordings at L1, aiming to infer the release of the high-energy particles and their relation to their driving accelerators. In doing so, we will further make use of unique L3 datasets (to be provided by the project), such as the E>100 MeV recordings of SOHO/ERNE and the E>500 MeV recordings of SOHO/EPHIN.
- Run modeling work of the coronal and interplanetary medium leading to this GLE including energetic particle transport, in order to disentangle the transport conditions of the particles under this very disturbed period.
- Explore the modelling potential of the interplanetary counterpart of the driving CME and its effect on the omnipresent GCRs that led to a deep FD of ~ 12% magnitude at ~ 6 GV particles.

¹ De-trended data from neutron monitors are available at <https://gle oulu.fi/>

Event 2: 08th of June 2024 SEP/Sub-GLE event

A M9.8 flare occurred on 08 June 2024 in AR13697 close to the West limb of the Sun (S17W72). Preliminary analysis of EUV data from the Solar Dynamics Observatory reveals a main CME eruption with clear post-flare loops as well as smaller scale transients caught up in the sheath during the initial expansion of the main event. Coronagraphic observations of the CME by SoHO and STEREO-A are of high quality revealing a clear broad CME shock that will be easily fitted by the shock modelling techniques in WP4. A first trajectory analysis shows that the CME was directed at Parker Solar Probe then situated at 0.6 AU, thereby providing an excellent opportunity to study an efficient particle accelerator in the inner heliosphere.

On this date a very strong SEP event ($E > 100$ MeV) was recorded at Earth by GOES and SOHO/ERNE. Given the most optimal magnetic connection STEREO-A also recorded enhanced proton and electron fluxes together with He, CNO and Fe that were observed at this time. One of the most important features of this event is the quiet long lasting background period prior to this event that allows for modeling of both the acceleration and transport of the energetic particles. Further to that this event was characterized as a sub-GLE² (Poluianov et al. 2017). The SPEARHEAD team will proceed with:

- A detail observational analysis of the in-situ particles in L1, combined with CME-shock reconstructions that will allow potentially coupling of the shock properties, to those of the observed particles.
- Research the transport conditions of the high-energy particles based on modeling and infer the acceleration and escape time of the particles, as well as their mean free path that better explains the observations for both protons and electrons.

Figure 0-5 – In-situ particle recordings by GOES $E > 10$ MeV (red line), $E > 50$ MeV (blue line) and $E > 100$ MeV (green line) (panel on the right hand side); the CME eruption of the 8 June 2024 (panel on the left hand side)

² Data for this sub-GLE will shortly appear in <https://gle oulu fi/>

Event 3: 17th of July 2021 Far Side Gamma Ray Event

A clear indication of the presence of >300MeV protons accelerated in the solar corona is the detection of >50MeV gamma rays (such as by the Fermi satellite) since such high radiation can only be produced during pion decay following the interaction of >300MeV protons with neutral hydrogen and helium. Because it is challenging to disentangle the flare and shock contributions to the acceleration process of high-energy particles, solar events during which the flare is occulted and situated far behind the limb are of particular interest because the shock contribution can be more easily isolated. The most extreme case such a behind the limb event occurred on 2021 July 17. This event was detected by STIX on board the Solar Orbiter which had a front view of the flare. The location of the flare was S20E140 in Stonyhurst heliographic coordinates. This event was associated with a broad CME and a coronal wave observed from both STEREO-A and SDO in extreme ultraviolet (EUV), with an onset on the visible disk which coincided with the LAT onset ([Pesce-Rollins et al. 2022](#)). For this event the SPEARHEAD team plans to:

- Perform a detailed observational analysis of the in-situ particles at Solar Orbiter and L1 that were magnetically connected to the Western flank of the CME, combined with CME-shock reconstructions that will allow potentially coupling of the shock properties, to those of the observed particles.
- Explore the possibility of modelling the 3-D particle transport from the shock surface towards the interplanetary medium and towards the solar disk, focusing in particular on particle impacts on the disk visible from Earth. This will allow us to gain new insights on the onset of the gamma/hard X rays measured by the Fermi-LAT during this event.

Figure 0-6 - From the SDO/AIA view, the flare on this day is highly occulted, and only the emission associated with the escaping CME is seen in the 193 Å running difference image (from [Pesce-Rollins et al. 2022](#))

Event 4: 14th of July 2012 Forbush Decrease

A large FD was recorded on the 14th of July 2012 by neutron monitors around the globe. This was the response to a very strong interplanetary CME that was initiated two days earlier on the 12th of July with a CDAW CME projected speed of 885 km/s (Shen et al., 2014). The driving shock arrived at Earth at ~ 18:00 UT on 14 July and the following ejecta was characterized by a closed structure, a magnetic cloud (MC). The FD started with the shock and reached its minimum within the MC. For 10 GV particles this was ~7%. Due to the long-lasting MC the FD was prolonged in time lasting for several days. The very slow recovery of the particles continued long after the passage of the MC on 17 July. For this event the SPEARHEAD team plans to:

- Analyse data from ground based neutron monitors, combined with time-shifted in-situ plasma (e.g. solar wind speed, temperature) and magnetic field measurements. This will allow for a direct interpretation of the effect of the ICME to the GCR measurements.
- Utilize the detail measurements of AMS-02 onboard the International Space Station (ISS) that provides direct in-situ measurements of the FD and explore the (possible) rigidity dependence.
- Model the FD in terms of the analytical Forbush Decrease Model (ForbMod) and investigate the obtained amplitudes of the event for different detectors (i.e. NMs, AMS-02).
- Model the flux-rope MC and propagate this within the interplanetary medium (assuming constant deceleration), counter compare the results to the in-situ measurements at L1 and couple the obtained results to the ForbMod.

Figure 0-7 - Evolution of the 12 July 2012 CME (top panel; from Shen et al., 2014) and the Forbush decrease identified in the AMS-02 data for different rigidities (energies); from CAU (bottom panel)

Event 5: 17th of May 2012 GLE 71 Event

On May 17th 2012 AR11476 was located at N13W83 and produced a strong M5.1 solar flare, associated with a fast ($V = 1582$ km/s) halo CME that was observed by SOHO/LASCO and STEREO coronagraphs. The elevated solar activity was further underlined with the presence of type II and III radio-bursts (see e.g. [Papaioannou et al., 2014](#)). The shock wave produced by the fast and wide CME was modelled in [Rouillard et al. \(2016\)](#) who argued that the highest energy particles could have been accelerated via diffusive-shock acceleration as the shock progressed through the tip of streamers and developed high Mach numbers. This interpretation was subsequently supported by advanced particle acceleration codes ([Afanasiev et al. 2018](#)).

Ground based detectors, as neutron monitors, with asymptotic look directions along the interplanetary magnetic field, characterized by low vertical cut-off rigidity are expected to provide the earliest onsets and highest increases in their counting rates. This was the case for GLE71, during which early onsets were marked by e.g. the Oulu (OULU), the Apatity (APTY), the Fort Smith (FSMT), and the South Pole (SOPO) neutron monitors.

An aspect of the event that has not been studied in sufficient detail was that the high-energy particles accelerated at the Sun propagated through a magnetic flux rope to reach the Earth and produce the GLE event. In situ data obtained at L1 shows clearly that the GLE occurred inside a magnetic flux rope. The latter had closed magnetic field geometry since counter-streaming suprathermal electrons were observed inside that flux rope. Interestingly, an analysis of the GLE reveals strong anisotropies with particles incoming from two directions.

For this event the **SPEARHEAD** team plans to improve our understanding of particle transport during GLE events:

- Analyse further data from ground based neutron monitors, combined with time-shifted in-situ plasma (e.g. solar wind speed, temperature) and magnetic field measurements. This will allow for a direct comparison of the flux rope structure passing over the Earth and the associated GLE.
- Model the magnetic connectivity between the coronal shock and the flux rope passing near the Earth
- Explore techniques to simulate the propagation of energetic particles through the flux rope and compare the resulting fluxes with those inferred from the analysis of the GLE.

Figure 0-8 – Cartoon of the plausible propagation of high energy particles through a magnetic flux rope that reach the Earth and produces the GLE event (figure taken from [Rouillard et al., 2016](#))

2 Conclusions

In this document, a list of CMEs to be analysed in detail by the **SPEARHEAD** project has been compiled and presented. This list constitutes **D4.1**. A priority order, based on the scientific merit of each event and strategic development of the project was decided by all *SPEARHEAD partners* in a collegial manner. Based on this first list, the teams can begin the scientific analysis related to the next deliverables. This list is likely to evolve throughout the project as additional powerful SEP events occur during the on-going solar maximum.

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List of Acronyms/Abbreviations

Acronym/ Abbreviation	Description
AMDA	Automated Multi-Dataset Analysis
ASCII	American Standard Code for Information Interchange
CDF	Common Data Format
CDPP	French National Data Center
CERN	European ORganization for Nuclear Research
CoC	Code of Conduct
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EPHIN	Electron Proton Helium Instrument
ERNE	Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron
ESA	European Space Agency
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse
FD	Forbush Decrease
FITS	Flexible Image Transport System
G4VM	Geant4 Virtual Machine
Geant4	GEometry ANd Tracking
GLE	Ground Level Enhancement
GOES	Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HEPAD	High Energy Proton and Alpha Detector
HET	High Energy Telescope
IHDEA	International Heliophysics Data Environment Alliance
ISTP	International Solar-Terrestrial Physics
KET	Kiel Electron Telescope
MeV	Megaelectronvolt
MSL	Mars Science Laboratory
NDC	National Data Center
NetCDF	Network Common Data Format
NMDB	Neutron Monitor DataBase

NOA	National Observatory of Athens
OS	Operating System
PyPI	Python Package Index
RAD	Radiation Assessment Detector
SC	Spacecraft
SDO	Solar Dynamics Observatory
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SIXS	Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
SQ	Science Question
SREM	Standard Radiation Environment Monitor
TO	Technical Objective
VDA	Velocity Dispersion Analysis
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package